

New therapeutic approaches against COVID-19: an approach that must be multidimensional and dynamic to counter the complications of this disease.

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Abstract

The recent pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV2 has brought the world to a halt. The damages done to the epithelial cells from the lungs by the virus and the immune system rapidly deteriorate in an ARDS in severe and critically ill patients. The only available “treatment” actually is a supportive treatment, no drugs having been studied enough to show enough evidence of efficacy against the virus or the complications done by that infection. The hope of a vaccine or the development of a new drug against the virus would be a real “game changer” as some has said, but developing a new drug takes time, time that we don’t have. As for the vaccine, we don’t even know how well it would work and might even be ineffective if the virus mutates too much. The possibility of a recurrent disease, like the annual flu, caused by the influenza virus was even raised by public health agencies around the world.

It is why this review is trying to find a way to mitigate the effect of the virus using already known and tested drugs to reduce the complications of the infection. We included potentially preventive treatments to lower the risk of becoming severely ill in the event the patient gets infected, treatments to lower the risk of deterioration of already severely ill and hospitalized cases to critical patients ventilated in the ICU and treatments to lower the mortality of those critical cases.

At the end of the review, we propose some recommendations. Some aim to help the research by creating easy ways to compare and validate the studies, like the creation of a COVID-19

complication risk score. Others, in our opinion, should be applied right away, because they might be helpful and don't have any associated risks of side effects or are only minor modifications of already treated patients for other conditions. Finally, other are suggestions of studied that should be conduct as soon as possible to validate the potential efficacy of known, used, approved and cheap drugs that could be used alone or in combination with one another to reduce the severity of the COVID-19.

Keywords: SARS-CoV2, COVID-19, COVID-19 Complication Risk Score (CCRS), ACE2, Diminazen aceturate, Vitamin D, Montelukast, Estrogen, Menopause, Hormonal replacement therapy, Combined oral contraception, ACE inhibitor, ARA, Azithromycin, Spironolactone, Metformin, rhACE2, Colchicine, Hydroxychloroquine, Chloroquine, C1INH, C1 esterase inhibitor, NSAID, Corticosteroid, Kevzara, Inhaled beta-agonist, Inhaled corticosteroid

Background

The SARS-CoV2 infection propagating around the world actually is probably one of the biggest modern threat we have ever faced. This virus is a biological wonder, his biomolecular adaptation making it a complex and lethal enemy that can't be battled with our usual approaches.

Even though it can infect anyone, not everyone will develop the same symptoms. It has a tendency to produce a significantly more severe illness for some group of patients. Elderlies are the most vulnerable population, the younger patients seeming protected from the critical illness. Usually, the newborns and the infants are more at risk to have complications when infected by other viruses, like the influenza. In the SARS-CoV2 pandemic, they seem to be much less at risk comparatively. Men are not more at risk to get infected, but, compared to women, they look more at risk to develop severe symptoms, to be admitted to the ICU, to need mechanical ventilation and to die from the infection. Patients with comorbidity, like HBP, diabetes, heart failure, COPD or immunosuppression, have higher risks to get sicker if they contract this virus. Interestingly, pregnant women don't seem to be more at risk with the SARS-CoV2; with the annual flu caused by the influenza virus, and even more during the H1N1 influenza pandemic, they were a more vulnerable population.

Understanding why this virus seems to target those groups more and the physio pathological mechanisms it uses to infect and to cause the chain of events that lead to the deterioration of the patients, allows us to explain what differences this virus presents and that makes it, like the SARS-CoV in 2003, so dangerous. By using these information, the studies about the SARS-CoV1, basis in molecular biology and human physiology, we could target where we should act to curb the downward spiral in which the patients are rapidly drove and try to stop this fall before the patient reaches the point of no return, because, at that point, it is unlikely he will be able to recover.

The most important point, in my opinion, is that a dynamic approach is necessary against this infection. Depending on the phase of the infection, its severity and the patient's characteristics, the treatment that could be beneficial might be harmful under other circumstances. The saying "treating the right patient with the right medication, at the right time and at the right place" has never been so true.

Another important point is that the approach we need to treat the COVID-19 must be multidimensional because the virus' effects, on our physiologic functions, are. We must defend on as many fronts as the virus is attacking us on.

It would explain why, up to now, most potential treatments are disappointing and studies seem to contradict one another. In this case, we must understand that it is unlikely that we will be able to find one molecule, one miracle drug, a "game changer" that would reverse the effects of the infection once it has started. We shouldn't aim for the homerun, but bet on a combination of multiple actions, that wouldn't necessarily be clinically significant individually, but, when combined in a multimodal therapeutic approach, might have synergistic effects to stop the natural development of the disease before it causes irreversible complications.

The actions we have to take can be divided into more specific objectives. The principle axis of this approach aim to cause the up-regulation and the activation of the ACE2, the modulation of the immune system (activating lymphocytes and inactivating the neutrophils) and the management of inflammation (by manipulating the cytokines, pro- vs anti-inflammatory). Other actions to support the vital functions and blunt the ARDS consequences would be interesting to review and study further in patients infected by SARS-CoV2.

The following sections will explain the mechanisms at stake permitting the SARS-CoV2 to infect us and cause complications as serious. Then, we will discuss why and how we should try to act on

the axis mentioned above. Finally, the reader will find recommendations drawn from the other sections.

Physiopathology

ACE2

The ACE2 has an important role in the physiology and the protection of the lung. Even if it was first known and studied for its role in degrading Angiotensin II (AngII) into Angiotensin (1-7) (Ang1-7), ACE2 is a protease that uses many pro-inflammatory messengers as substrates. Also, it is able to transform the Angiotensin I (AngI) to Angiotensin (1-9) (Ang1-9). While AngII, by binding to the AT1R receptors, has pro-inflammatory, pro-fibrotic, vasoconstrictor and proliferative effects, AngI, Ang1-7, Ang1-9 and AngIII, by binding to the AT2R receptors, have anti-inflammatory, anti-fibrotic, anti-proliferative and vasodilator (by activating the NO synthase) effects. By understanding the exponential effect of the cascade of inflammation, one can visualize what would happen if many ACE2 were inactivated; the pro-inflammatory cytokines and other messengers would attract many leukocytes (mainly, neutrophils and macrophages) that would produce much more inflammatory mediators, and so on, without being down-regulated. This unopposed chain-reaction, observed in some of the COVID-19 and SARS-CoV1 infection, is called a cytokine storm.

COVID-19's chain-reaction toward the ARDS

The SARS-CoV2 (like the SARS-CoV1) use the ACE2 to enter the cells, its glycoprotein-S binding to the active site. The ACE2 is expressed in many organs but has a higher expression in the type 1 and type 2 alveolar epithelial cells. The type 1 borders the alveoli and enables the gas exchanges and the type 2 is responsible for, among other things, the surfactant's production.

The infected cells will eventually be destroyed and the cell lysis will release chemokines that will attract and then activate neutrophils, macrophages and dendritic cells; the innate immune system first line of defense. In turn, these cells will release proteolytic enzymes, free radicals, superoxide ions and even more pro-inflammatory cytokines. These chemicals, supposed to attack the invaders, will also damage the adjacent cells, alveolar epithelial cells, and cause their lysis, causing, once again, some more pro-inflammatory messengers to be released.

The resulting inflammation added to the damage to alveolar and endothelial cells will result in an important increase in capillary permeability and the leakage of proteins-rich fluid to the interstitial space and into the alveoli. This leakage will lower the oncotic gradient that was regulating the movement of fluid between the plasma and the extravascular compartment. These 2 changes will result in a great outflow of fluid toward the interstitial space, way above what the lymphatic system can reabsorb, quickly flooding the alveoli, causing an acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS).

In the ARDS, the blood, already poor in oxygen, that pass through the damaged alveoli won't be able to receive any oxygen. It will then mix with the O₂-rich blood that went through the normal alveoli, causing a drop in SaO₂. Even if we supplement the patient with a higher FiO₂, the increase in SaO₂ won't be significant, the blood that passed by the unaffected alveoli, being already at a saturation of around 100%. This explain why patients with ARDS are so hard to oxygenate and might need to be put on mechanical ventilation to sustain the blood's oxygenation and reduce the respiratory workload. Unfortunately, the pulmonary compliance being lower, barotraumas aren't uncommon and cause the destruction of more alveolar epithelial cells, perpetuating and aggravating the ARDS.

The destruction of the type 2 alveolar epithelial cells causes a decrease in surfactant production. Other protease released during the inflammatory process can inactivate the little surfactant that was left. This will result in the closing of the alveoli, during the expiration, and the reopening during the inspiration, atelectasis, damaging the epithelial cells even more.

This explains why the ARDS is so thought to treat, our only treatments being mostly the respiratory support and the reversal of the underlying cause. The mortality rate of ARDS varies between 25-35% for mild ARDS and 45-50% with severe ARDS.

In COVID-19, one of our only protection's mechanism, the ACE2, is sequestered and down-regulated by the virus leaving us defenseless and unable to slow down the rapidly progressing inflammation. This might explain why the mortality rate in patients who developed ARDS following a COVID-19 infection was 52,4% in a retrospective cohort study¹, but was sometime even higher if we consider only the patients necessitating intubation and mechanical ventilation in the ICU for a severe ARDS, ranging from 85% to 97% .^{2,3}

The second wave: the humoral response?

As if it wasn't enough, it is possible that the humoral response, the production of antibody, could be harmful in some cases. When we look at the natural evolution of the SARS-CoV1 in 2003, a worsening in the patient condition could be noted when the production of antibodies was starting and/or amplifying, even if the virus titer was decreasing.⁴

One possible explanation can be found in the analysis of a test made while developing a vaccine against SARS-CoV1. Interestingly, the vaccine directed against the glycoprotein S, was protecting the mice effectively when subsequently re-exposed to the virus, but the one targeting the protein N, an immune-dominant molecule from the nucleocapside that induce a cell-mediated and a humoral reaction, increased the risk of developing a severe pneumonia if the mice were re-

exposed to the same virus.⁵ They found that these antibodies were causing an elevation of some pro-inflammatory cytokines (IFN-gamma, IL-2, -4 and -5) that caused neutrophils, eosinophils and lymphocytes recruitment in the lungs. All these leukocytes, by releasing more cytokines, were able to give another chance to initiate a cytokine storm and to damage the lung even further. The vaccine against the protein N was not able to prevent the attachment of the virus to the ACE2, lowering even more the production of IL-10 and TGF-beta, anti-inflammatory cytokine.

This could explain why, in some patient, the arrival of the “cavalry”, instead of decreasing the damage done to the lungs by resolving the initial cause, perpetuate the ARDS even though it seems to be efficiently attacking the virus, its titer falling at that moment.

This reaction has not been reported, not even studied, for the SARS-CoV2, but a deterioration seen in many patients mechanically ventilated in the ICU seems to happen with a time frame equivalent to the one in SARS-CoV1 infection.

In summary, because the COVID-19 is inactivating the ACE2, one really important retroaction mechanism, which allows us to control and modulate the inflammation caused by the damages induced by the virus and our own immune system, is disrupted. Nothing is left to prevent the patient’s fall in the down-ward spiral of inflammation, especially if our immune system “chooses” the wrong antigen to mount the humoral response. But now let’s see how we could try to manipulate and “hack” our response to avoid these complications.

Potential solutions

Up-regulation of ACE2

The study by Li et al (2006) showed clearly that the up-regulation of ACE2 had beneficial effects on the outcomes of rats with LPS-induced ARDS.⁶ But can we generalize these results in SARS-CoV2 infection?

Estrogen

One question was asked a lot in the beginning of the pandemic, after we found out the receptor used by the virus to infect the cells was ACE2. Is over-expressing ACE2 a protective factor, permitting us to temper the cytokine storm, or a risk factor, giving the virus an easier access to our cells? The actual clues, even though mostly indirect, seem to suggest the first possibility.

First, let's look at the gap between the ratio of COVID-19 cases and the ratio of mortality between men and women. Men represent 58% of cases, but 72% of death. Many differences in the behavior of men and women were used to explain that gap, the rate of smoking, the average of time men wash their hands or the amount of men not respecting the public health recommendations; men being more inclined to have reckless behaviors than women. But let's compare our situation to the one in 2003, the SARS-CoV1 pandemic. In that situation too, the mortality rate was higher in men. A study using mice was showing the same results, except in one situation, when the mice were gonadectomised or were given estrogen-receptor blockers. In these 2 situations, the rate of severe illness and of mortality were both equivalent in males and females.⁷ We can come to the conclusion that it is the sexual hormones that impact the severity and mortality rate from the SARS-CoV1 infection and that explain the statistics presented earlier, not the behavior. That study has shown that the activation of the estrogen-receptor is a key factor in women's relative protection against SARS-CoV1. When they were activated, less

macrophages/monocytes were activated, less neutrophils were found in the lungs, the virus titer was lower and there was less vascular leakage and less pulmonary edema. The amount of T and B lymphocytes or their response weren't affected by the presence or absence of estrogen. The similarity between SARS-CoV1 and 2, in function and epidemiology, makes it possible to generalize from one to the other with strong confidence.

Another hypothesis was that, because the ACE2 gene is on the X chromosome, women could have more ACE2 or have better odds of having at least one gene variant that functions optimally. Other genes that might influence the immune system are also on the X chromosome. We can refute this hypothesis, the manipulations made in Channappanavar et al's experimentation having no influence on the amount of X chromosome in their mice.

But what effect has estrogen on the clinical course and outcome? A few hypotheses were suggested to explain this effect. Some experts pretend that women have a more efficient immune system against viral infection. Estrogen could promote a stronger adaptive response from the T lymphocytes and enabling a better recruitment of neutrophils. High concentrations of estrogen, like those found during the pregnancy, have some immunosuppressive effects, while lower concentrations act as a stimulant for the immune system. Androgen would always have immunosuppressive effects, but probably less than estrogen's. If this hypothesis is true, the gender disparity in morbidity and mortality observed in the COVID-19 and the SARS in 2003 would be present in other great viral pandemics, like influenza's (annual or H1N1). Even if a small tendency seems to demonstrate the exactness of the hypothesis, a WHO's review produced in 2010⁸ showed a great variability in the data from different countries or age groups. But if we use the data from the countries using better methodology and that are comparable to the data we have for SARS-CoV1 or COVID-19 pandemics, they do not come close to the one seen in the COVID pandemic. Yet, the same mechanisms are used to defend against these viral infections and to

prevent the same complications, like the ARDS, that would result from the same kind of cytokine storm. One huge difference between these viruses is the molecule they bind to infect our cells, the SARS-CoV2 using ACE2. A study in rats showed that even if male and female young adult rats had an ACE2 expression that seemed equivalent, the reduction, as they were aging, was significantly bigger in male than female, causing a significant difference between genders in the older age groups⁹. In the ACE2 gene expression regulatory sequence, we can find many binding sites for the estrogen receptors, but only a few for the androgen receptors. The amount of ACE2 correlate in vivo with the increase in estrogen level and decrease in androgen level in transgender men taking hormonal therapy¹⁰. This theory has another benefit; it would explain why pregnant women, usually more fragile to influenza pandemics, do not seem to be more at risk in the actual pandemic, being flooded in estrogen.

Cytokines

The massive increase in inflammatory cytokines (IL-2, -7, -10, G-CSF, IP-10, MCP-1, MIP-1a and TNF-alpha) in patients severely ill seems to downregulate the ACE2 expression too¹⁰. The SARS-CoV1 infection, in mice, raise the production of ACE2's mRNA with a low viral titer and in the first few days. But as the virus titer increase, the ACE2's mRNA is massively downregulated. The same phenomenon can be observed from the 4th day and after, even with the smallest viral titer. In studies comparing the severity of pulmonary damage in ACE2-KO mice and wild type, following an infection by SARS-CoV1, H5N1-, H7N9- influenza or acid inhalation, the ACE2-KO mice always had more damage and more severe pneumonia. But even the wild type mice had a decrease in

ACE2 expression in the studies, probably because of the production of the cytokines mentioned above¹¹⁻¹⁴.

ACE-inhibitors and ARBs

A systematic review and meta-analysis by Caldeira et al (2012), showed that, even if we adjust for risk factors and age, the use of ACEI, but not ARB, brings a 34% decrease in risk of pneumonia compared to the control group. It was a robust, statistically and clinically significant effect. A decrease in the pneumonia associated mortality rate, was also observed but not with as much robustness and in both ARBs and ACEIs. The effect was even greater in Asian patient.¹⁵

AngII is known to up-regulate the expression of ACE and downregulate the ACE2 through its action on one of the AT1R receptor in the heart¹⁶. ACEI prevents the transformation of AngI to AngII. ARB is known to block AT1R but stimulate AT2R and AT4R. In this study, he found that both seemed to increase ACE2 expression. ACEI reduced the amount of AngII and, so reduced the downregulation of ACE2, ARBs by doing the exact opposite effect of AngII, mimicked the effect of Ang(1-7) or Ang(1-9).

Vitamin D

A study using rats, demonstrated that the administration of vitamin D was raising the quantity of mRNA and the expression of ACE2 and that these effects were dose dependant. The group receiving the biggest dose was receiving 25ug/kg, the equivalent of a 70000 UI for a 70kg human. They induced ARDS by injecting LPS to rats having received various doses of vitamin D. Those having received vitamin D had milder symptoms of respiratory distress and the physiopathological changes in the lung were less important than those of the control group. The rats having received the vitamin D, with or without LPS, had more mRNA and protein for both ACE2 and VDR (vitamin D receptor)¹⁷. This suggest a positive retroaction amplification response of vitamin D by having

cells that are more sensitive to vitamin D when there is more vitamin D. We might imagine a relation between vitamin D and ACE2 that is more exponential than linear when we increase the doses.

In human, a RCT was trying to determine if the preventive supplementation of vitamin D in patients at risk for ARDS and with a less than 50 ng/ml of vitamin D in their blood test could prevent acute lung injury (PETAL Network, Preventive and Early Treatment of Acute Lung injury). They finished the collection of the data in November 2019 and the results are not yet published. But a study, by Dancer et al, showed that in patient with ARDS, vitamin D deficiency was ubiquitous. Inducing a deficiency, in animal models, caused an exaggerated inflammatory response with more damage to alveolar epithelial cells and more hypoxemia. In patients waiting to have an esophagectomy, the aggressive repletion of vitamin D deficiency before the operation was reducing significantly the damage to the pulmonary capillaries¹⁸. The exact mechanism isn't yet known, but we do know that the expression of approximately 600 genes, in epithelial cells, is modulated by the binding of vitamin D to his receptor.

In summary, many studies seem to demonstrate that, in the setting of acute lung injury, independently of the cause, higher levels of ACE2 means higher chances of favorable outcomes. It is true in SARS-CoV1 too, and we can postulate the hypothesis that it is most likely true with the SARS-CoV2. Estrogen, and in a less powerful manner, androgen, vitamin D, another steroidal hormone, the use of ACEIs and ARBs are all able to upregulate the ACE2 in the lungs and shift the balance towards the anti-inflammatory messengers, reducing the inflammation and damage to the lungs.

ACE2 activation

Now that we have well establish that the more ACE2 is expressed, the better the odds of a good outcome, let's evaluate the possibility to over-activate it artificially.

The diminazen aceturate (DA) is thought to catalyze the ACE2 activity. It's an old medication, still used in veterinary medicine, which was used, mostly in Africa, to treat trypanosomiasis, a disease caused by a protozoan transmitted by the tsetse fly (well known as the human sleeping sickness).

The DA can modulate the host immune response in this disease. A study has demonstrated that DA was preventing the cytokine storm known to be triggered by this infection. It was decreasing the production of many pro-inflammatory cytokine, IFN-gamma, IL-6, -12 and all TNF. DA was able to efficiently neutralize the over stimulation of the immune system in that parasitic infection and in the administration of LPS (used to simulate a septic shock), preventing the apparition of the systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS)¹⁹.

Other studies demonstrated that DA has an effect on hepatic fibrosis and pulmonary hypertension, then again, reducing the hyperactive response of the immune system and its pro-fibrotic effect^{20,21}. The mechanism enabling the DA effect on inflammation depend on its ability to temper the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, to inactivate some cells (like the dendritic cell) and to reduce the migration of cells from the intravascular compartment to the interstitial space. But how DA can accomplish this feat is still debated.

According to Haber et al, the action mechanism is independent from ACE2. In that study, they gave, to ACE2-KO mice and their wild-type counterpart, infusion of AngII to produce a HBP model. They compared the effect of rhACE2 (recombinant human ACE2, the active protease portion of the enzyme) compared to the effect of XNT (another potential ACE2 activator) and to a control group. Both groups showed a rapid normalization of the BP, in ACE2-KO and WT. They concluded

that if the BP was normalized in ACE2-KO mice, it wasn't the activation nor the overexpression on ACE2 that was normalizing the BP when XNT was given. The DA was not tested under these conditions. They then tested XNT and DA in vitro. They mixed them with rhACE2 and added a substrate that would become fluorescent when cleaved. Neither "activators" did any better than the control²².

On the other hand, Hernandez Prada et al had different results in the same experiment, they observed that the rhACE2 activity doubled with DA²³. No explanations were given to clarify why their results were different. Finally, in a study by Shenoy et al, DA's protective effect on pulmonary fibrosis was completely cancelled when adding a strong ACE2 inhibitor²¹. This could prove that DA's effects are linked to ACE2, at least, in vivo. The effect could come from the upregulation of the ACE2 instead of its activation, but that would not explain Hernandez Prada's results. Another possibility would be that the activation of ACE2 by DA could be substrate-specific or -dependant. Its catalytic effect could be dependent on the presence of other surface or cytoplasmic molecules, making it ineffective in vitro. For example, the metformin activates the MAPk that phosphorylates the insulin receptor increasing its affinity to insulin. If DA's action mechanism necessitates binding of the DA to the inactive portion of ACE2, then, cleaving ACE2 to produce rhACE2, would cause DA to be ineffective with rhACE2 and that would mean that DA should have an effect in vivo on ACE2 but not on rhACE2.

Anyway, given all the studies on DA in pathologies caused by cytokine storms, and the really good results it usually shows, good results in controlling ARDS 's cytokine storm could be expected, and maybe even more dramatically in COVID-19's ARDS.

Other important points are that DA already exists and is cheap. Doctors and national control programs of endemic country for trypanosomiasis used it because it was effective and well

tolerated in humans. They stopped using DA because of drug-resistances and the commercialisation of other drugs able to treat these resistant strains of trypanosome. In most species, the therapeutic doses (between 3,5 and 7 mg/kg) rarely shows any sign of toxicity. The therapeutic index is large in most animal species; cows, for example, can tolerate doses up to 21mg/kg without any toxicity. Inversely, dogs and camels show signs of toxicity at therapeutic doses. A dose of 7 mg/kg in camels or 10 mg/kg in dogs can cause lesions to the digestive, respiratory, musculoskeletal and nervous system. In rodents, a little hypotension could be observed. Otherwise, DA is well tolerated in other mammals. Traces of DA were found in milk of a lactating goat. Animal studies show no sign of teratogenicity. DA showed no mutagenic effect in *Salmonella typhimurium* but could have some in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. In human, a small study with 17 patients showed no sign of toxicity. In a second one, with 99 patient, no other side effects, others than those of other anti-parasitic drugs, like suramine, were reported. A case report showed 1 case of acute idiopathic polyneuritis (Guillain-Barre syndrome). According to doctors having used it with many patients, the only side effects could be a low grade fever and nausea.²⁴

rhACE2

A pilot clinical trial by Khan et al used rhACE2 to treat ARDS²⁵. The patients were admitted in ICU of 10 hospitals in Canada and USA for ARDS, were between 18 and 80 years old and has been mechanically ventilated for less than 72h. They were randomized, the control group receiving only respiratory support and the other group had the same support but received rhACE2 twice a day for 3 days (IV dose of 0,4 mg/kg). They stopped the study at 39 patients, because even if some parameters were getting better, the patients weren't. In the study, the initial causes of ARDS were heteroclite in both group; sepsis, pneumonia, aspiration and some others, no SARS-CoV1 or 2. In addition, even though they were randomized, both groups weren't homogenous. The SOFA score

of the rhACE2 group and their AngII level were higher and their SaO₂, lower at randomization. In the treated group, the AngII level dropped drastically and the Ang(1-7) quickly raised. The level of IL-6 had a tendency to be lower with the rhACE2. The concentration of surfactant's D protein was significantly higher. On the other hand, no differences in PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio, in oxygenation index or in the outcome were observed.

Even if the results were not as good as predicted, we must highlight some important divergences between the actual pandemic and this study. First, the initial causes of ARDS might prevent us from generalizing the results from the study to the SARS-CoV2 infection. The ARDS weren't caused by a virus binding the ACE2 receptor and downregulating it. The magnitude of the effect might be bigger in a SARS-CoV2 infection because the groups would be more different. Another way rhACE2 could help is by acting as a decoy molecule preventing the virus to bind the ACE2 on the cells' surfaces and penetrate the membrane, but only if the virus can bind the rhACE2 (and that hasn't been demonstrated yet). Secondly, the dose, the timing of the dose's administration and its frequency might not have been optimal. Higher doses weren't tested in this study. The patients were already in the ICU and under mechanical ventilation when they were first treated. The way ARDS is amplified over time make it harder to reverse the later the treatment is received. In another study, the rapid administration of rhACE2 to piglets with LPS-induced ARDS showed an improvement in the PaO₂, the blood flow distribution and the levels of TNF-alpha and AngII²⁶. The rhACE2 half-life seemed to be around 10h in human²⁷; 12h intervals between dose might have been too long and lower the effect's size.

Leukocytes and Cytokines modulation

Many epidemiologic data and biomolecular knowledge can make us suspect that modifying the immune response triggered by the SARS-CoV2 could limit the damage done to the lung and prevent the progression toward the ARDS or its worsening.

In recent articles both looking at characteristics of COVID-19 + patients and their outcomes, higher was the leukocyte count, worse was the prognostic. The same relation was seen with neutrophils. Inversely, even if most patient had lymphopenia, lowest quantities meant worst outcomes. A reduced quantity of CD4+ and CD8+ lymphocytes predicted a bad evolution^{2,28}.

During the SARS in 2003, the same observations were made. These anomalies were detected at the patient arrival at the hospital. A higher mortality rate was also noted in patients that started to produce antibodies early, compared to patients that had started later⁴.

Another observation made in COVID-19 is that, even though newborns and infants are usually at risk in most respiratory virus pandemics (like RSV or influenza), they don't seem to be sicker in COVID-19. Taking into account the risk factors stated above, their leukocytes profile might help their prognostic if they get infected by COVID-19. The relative amount of lymphocytes, in percentage, is higher until the age of 12, the percentage of neutrophils is lower. This difference is even more obvious in child under 2 years old. It's not uncommon in pediatrics to have patients with a mild idiopathic neutropenia, with no immunologic deficit. Children seems to better temper their immune response compared to adults. We just have to look at the epidemiology of most auto-immunes diseases; most of them have their first spike in prevalence after puberty, mostly in the mid-twenties. So, it seems logical to try replicating the child's immune response in adults.

Even if neutrophils are one of the main actors involve in the immune response causing ARDS, patients in severe neutropenia has been known to sometime end up in ARDS anyway by the same

kind of immune over-reaction leading to cytokine storm²⁹. Even if mild neutropenia is a protective factor in SARS-CoV2 infection, and that neutrophils seem like a promising target to stop the immune cascade leading to ARDS, it would probably be more effective if used early in the clinical course of the disease. Once the spiral has started and neutrophils have already started to migrate and release chemical mediators and proteolytic enzymes, the system inertia might be hard to stop or even slow down. Even if an action targeting neutrophils might be helpful, the fact that the inflammation leading to ARDS can happen in neutropenic patient tells us that it might be, if used alone, ineffective.

Colchicine is being studied by Dr Tardif, from the Montreal Heart Institute and in Greece by Deftereos et al³⁰. The use of colchicine seems to be appropriate in COVID-19 patients; it is known to block the neutrophils migration, their activation, their capacity to release their chemical mediators and enzymes, by stabilizing the microtubules, and their production of IL-1beta. Because colchicine effect seems concentrated mainly on neutrophils, not suppressing the whole immune system, its use looks promising.

The NSAID are able to attenuate neutrophils action, mainly their aggregation on the site of infection, the generation of superoxide ions and the release of lysosomal enzymes. NSAID action also affect lymphocytes' activity. Considering the important effect of a drop in the amount of lymphocytes on the mortality rate, it seems wiser to stay away from NSAID to treat COVID-19 symptoms. An editorial by Little summarize well the data advising against the use of that type of medication³¹.

The same logic can be applied to the sarilunab, an IL-6 receptor antagonist, known for its action on neutrophils, inactivating them, and for its inhibitory effect on the promotion of the differentiation of B lymphocytes into plasma B cells and the release of antibodies. The idea of

blocking the activation of those 2 cell lines might sound good, but IL-6 also has a role in the differentiation of CD4+ T lymphocytes. Weaning the CD4+ T lymphocytes of all signals from IL-6 cause the apoptosis of the cells in vitro³². Lymphopenia, and even more the decrease of the CD4+ lymphocytes, was one of the strongest predictive factors of a bad prognostic in COVID-19. The use of this agent must be done with great caution.

Data on systemic corticotherapy against MERV and SARS-CoV1 infections showed that the time to get rid of the virus was prolonged when it was administered, that patients treated had higher risk of being mechanically ventilated and a higher mortality rate³³⁻³⁷. In influenza pandemics, their use increase mortality if used widely, without any other clear indications, like exacerbation of underlying asthma or COPD. Observational studies from China showed that some patients were getting better following the administration of corticosteroids, but they lacked the presence of a control-group to compare^{1-3,28}. Following the clinical data, the Society of critical care medicine (SCCM) discourage the use of corticosteroids in patients with mild, moderated or severe illness. The SCCM emit a weak recommendation about systemic corticosteroid use in critically ill patients, but only small doses for a short period of time and only in the first 14 days from the onset of symptoms. They added that further studies need to be done to better evaluate the balance of pros and cons, particularly in SARS-CoV2 infections.

Even if inhaled corticosteroid is not part of the therapeutic arsenal used against COVID-19, a study seemed to demonstrate that their use, combined with long-acting beta-agonist, could help prevent the occurrence of ARDS³⁸. Unfortunately, this study regrouped many different pathologies that can evolve to ARDS, not only viral pneumonias, and no SARS-CoV1 or 2. Even if the study was a double blind randomized study, a statistical anomaly was introduced in the study. The placebo group had 14 patients in shock at randomization against only 3 in the treatment group. The outcomes showed that 7 patients developed ARDS in the placebo group against 0 in

the treatment group. More patients in the placebo group necessitated mechanical ventilation (53% vs 21%). Even if these results are really interesting, the confidence in the validity and reproducibility of the study is low. Additionally, the use of inhalators and nebulized treatment can generate aerosol that can potentially contaminate health care workers. Taking everything into account, we think the risks outweigh the benefits, even more if we consider it from a public health point of view.

Even if the direct action on the immune system should be carefully used, a targeted and coordinated immunomodulation might help us tip the balance in favor of some actors of the immune system that would help to reduce the mortality risk, while preventing other cells of having deleterious effects on the patient. We should be careful not to immunosuppress the patient completely, leaving him without any defenses against the virus or other complications like secondary bacterial pneumonia or opportunistic infections, even to reactivation of latent viruses or mycobacterias. The subtle difference between immunomodulation and immunosuppression lies exactly there. A wide immunosuppression would harm the activation of other leukocytes, mainly lymphocytes, which are useful in the elimination of the virus or to modulate the immune system, like CD4+ T lymphocytes, cytotoxic T lymphocytes or NK cells.

Another way to tip the balance in favor of lymphocytes would be to promote their activation. If we could promote a more efficient immune response against SARS-CoV2, before it gets the chance of doing a lot of damage to the alveolar epithelial cells, we could minimize the release of pro-inflammatory cytokine attracting and activating the neutrophils. An important cell in the innate immune system against virus infections is the NK cell. It can recognize infected cells and, by perforating its membrane and sending chemical messengers, cause the destruction of the host infected cell, preventing the virus replication and the infection of neighbouring cells. A systematic review analyzed studies on the NK cell activation. They find promising results showing an

activation by vitamin D, vitamin B12, retinoic acid, curcuma, red-ginseng and phytoestrogens³⁹. Vitamin D deficiency being ubiquitous in Canada and northern states of the USA and some country of Europe, B12 deficiency being frequent in the elderly, and the supplementation in these 2 vitamins not representing any risk for the patient, they should be given to the most vulnerable populations. Even if their effect is small or, even, minimal, and that their NNT is high, their low cost could make the benefits/cost ratio in favor of the intervention. As for the other natural health product, the effectiveness might vary in function of the origin or the purity of the product and doses are difficult to generalize. High standard studies would need to be done before we could consider them seriously.

Antiviral drugs

Most studies on the natural history of SARS-CoV1 and 2 tend to demonstrate that, in patients who already started to see their respiratory function deteriorate and are already on their way toward ARDS, getting rid of the virus does not correlate with the patients getting better significantly. It might be logical that the prevention of damage to the lung by the blockage of the virus' penetration into the cells or the stop of its replication should create less inflammation and lead to a milder illness, but once the inflammation process has started, removing the virus from the equation doesn't seem to affect the amplifying inflammatory response caused by the positive retroaction of neutrophils producing cytokines attracting neutrophils that release cytokines, and so on. Unfortunately, the time it takes symptoms to appear and to bring the patients to seek health care, added to the time to make the PCR test to detect the presence of SARS-CoV2 and receive the results, or even worst, the time it takes patients to deteriorate enough to consult in the emergency room, the window of opportunity might have already closed. This hypothesis could explain why some antiviral drugs, working well in vitro or that should be working well against this

virus when we analyze their mechanism of action, have disappointing results in the clinical trials on SARS-CoV1 and 2.

To have a bigger effect, we could need to treat earlier. Many treatments against viruses need to be initiated quickly after the first symptoms or signs of the disease. The longer we wait before treating the less effective the treatment gets. We just have to think about HSV's cold sore or VZV's zona. Starting antivirals that early in COVID-19 might not be, on a large scale, really cost-efficient, if we consider the fact that most patients end up being asymptomatic or having mild to moderate symptoms and that, at that time, it could be difficult to predict the patient's evolution toward a mild vs severe illness. Using antiviral this way would probably means a really high NNT, because we wouldn't be selecting patients that would, without any doubt, benefit the treatment and end up treating patients that would not have needed the treatment to get better. On the other hand, antiretroviral drugs usually have side effects and a risk of toxicity that could lead to a NNH smaller than the NNT. The risks would be even higher if used in elderly patients, even worst with comorbidities, if we take into account that they usually have a reduced drug's elimination's rate.

Finally, antiretroviral drugs, like ribavirin, are usually expensive. This medication, used in the SARS pandemic in 2003, without any benefits, costs, according to Uptodate, approximately 27 000 US\$ per day. Using it, without any clear proofs of a positive effect on the survival of patient, on a large scale, doesn't seem like the most cost effective treatment. Even if we use a cheaper antiviral drug, like lopinavir/ritonavir, a treatment combining 2 antiretroviral drugs used against HIV, which is

studied in a RCT to see its effect on COVID-19, its cost, 20\$ per day or 140 to 200\$ for the whole treatment, is 100 times higher than Diminazen Aceturate.

In summary, as of today, antiviral drugs have not shown any benefit against SARS-CoV1 and 2, are costly and might cause sides effects. That's why without any other study proving the opposite, antiviral drugs should not be use routinely in COVID-19.

Miscellaneous therapies

Chloroquine/Hydroxychloroquine

Chloroquine, an antimalarial agent, is able to slow the viral replication by inhibiting the DNA- and RNA-polymerase. It has some minor effect inhibiting prostaglandin's actions. Its therapeutic index is narrow, and it can have serious cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, hematologic, neurological, psychiatric and ophthalmologic consequences and has many drug-drug interactions. Chloroquine is actually under investigation and using the same logic than the one used with antiviral drugs, slowing down the virus or, even, clearing the infection, once inflammation has progress to a stage where it amplifies by itself, might not be the best approach.

Hydroxychloroquine inhibit neutrophils motility, eosinophil chemotaxis and can interfere with the complement's cascade activation by the binding of antibody to antigen. These characteristics make hydroxychloroquine a better candidate compared to chloroquine. It could be useful early on, to neutralize neutrophils, or a little later, when a patient is starting to have more circulating antibodies, a moment when some critically ill patients tend to deteriorate. But, it has been known to reduce CD4+ T lymphocytes by inducing their apoptosis. It has been used in T-lymphocyte-mediated autoimmune disease like Lupus or corticosteroid-resistant Graft-vs-host disease. At

least, its action on the immune system is more an immunomodulation, not an immunosuppression.

A methodically well-designed study on hydroxychloroquine is being made in Europe actually. It is going to be interesting to see if neutrophils inactivation will be enough to compensate the lymphocytes decreasing count. Once the efficacy established, it will be easier to evaluate the risk/benefice ratio, hydroxychloroquine having some serious side effects (cardiac failure, bone marrow suppression, anemia, retinal toxicity, etc.) In ARDS, anemia tends to raise mortality, the blood already being poor in oxygen because of the ARDS.

Azithromycine

Azithromycin is a macrolide with antibiotic and anti-inflammatory effects. It was studied in some animal models of ARDS and seemed beneficial thanks to its anti-inflammatory properties. A retrospective observational study compared 47 patients having received a macrolide (azithromycin or erythromycin) in the first 24h following the diagnostic of ARDS to 188 patients having received another antibiotic or none. They showed a reduction of the mortality 180 days later (HR – 0,46 (0,23-0,92)) and better odds of being successfully wean off mechanical ventilation (HR 1,93 (1,18-3,17)). Fluoroquinolone and cephalosporin had no effect on these 2 outcomes. Macrolides would be able to inhibit the phospholipase-A2's action, lowering the production of arachidonic acid, a powerful promotor of inflammation who can upregulate the production of prostaglandins, thromboxane and leukotrienes⁴⁰. Because Azithromycin is usually well tolerated, rarely causing serious side effects, it is probably a drug that should be studied against COVID-19.

Montelukast

Leukotrienes are molecules which have a strong chemotaxis effect on neutrophils. Montelukast being a leukotriene receptor agonist, it blocks the effect of leukotriene on neutrophils and other

leukocytes, lowering the number of inflammatory cells on the site of inflammation and their release of cytokines.

A recent study has demonstrated that, in mice to which was administered LPS to mimic ARDS, the BAL of mice treated with Montelukast showed less neutrophils, macrophages and lymphocytes and less IL-6, -7 and TNF-alpha. The same observations were true in the pulmonary parenchyma. In vitro, Montelukast was able to decrease human neutrophils' activation⁴¹.

Its tolerability is really good, particularly in an inpatient setting and even more with patients sedated while on ventilators. The most "dangerous" adverse reactions are neuropsychiatric symptoms (agitation, abnormal dreams, attention deficit, disorientation, depression, anxiety, irritability, restlessness, and hallucinations). They start in a median of 5 days and, on discontinuation, stop on the 2nd day (median). Suicidal ideation and behavior, mainly in teenagers, were reported, but a 2018 review by Khalid et al showed strong evidences of the absence of a positive association between Montelukast and suicidal behaviors on a population level⁴².

Mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists

Spirolactone, amiloride and eplerenone are blocking the binding of aldosterone to its receptors. Aldosterone's secretion is stimulated by AngII. It promotes sodium reabsorption in kidneys, causing water and sodium retention helping to maintain a sufficient blood pressure.

Aldosterone also has proinflammatory and profibrotic effects. It causes an increase in cytokines, a decrease in insulin sensitivity and a vasoconstriction, by inhibiting the NO synthase activity, particularly in the coronary arteries.

A study in an ARDS rat model showed that spironolactone was improving the rats PaO₂/FiO₂, was lowering BNP and decreasing the ARDS severity score⁴³. A second study by the same group

confirmed the results. They observed an improvement in PO₂, SpO₂, pH, PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio in the spironolactone group that was comparable to surfactant administration. Acute phase reactants (IL-1beta, TNF-alpha, HMGB1 and CRP) were all decreased significantly by spironolactone and surfactant compared to controls and only IL-1beta had a bigger decrease with the surfactant. Damage to the lungs was prevented at 24h with the administration of a single dose of spironolactone early after the ARDS was induced⁴⁴.

Spironolactone is a relatively safe drug, but it should be noted that the concomitant use of heparin or LMWH is counter-indicated. It can also cause an electrolyte imbalance that should be monitored by serial analysis.

C1 esterase inhibitor (C1INH)

This human blood derived produce is used to treat hereditary angioedema. It targets many pro-inflammatory molecules. It can also bind histones, proteins found in the nucleus, binding the DNA and packaging it to reduce its length. In cell lysis, histones are released and cause a chain reaction promoting inflammation, but C1INH can prevent this effect. C1INH can stop the complement and the coagulation cascades (by inhibiting the coagulation factor XIIa).

A study showed that, in a dog model of sepsis (and ARDS), pulmonary dysfunction was reduced by an infusion of C1INH. Even if the SaO₂/FiO₂ ratio was not normalized by the treatment, intra pulmonary shunt, hypoxia and DIVC were prevented⁴⁵.

The results of a RCT with 61 ICU patients with sepsis showed interesting points. The experimental group received C1INH in addition to conventional treatment. The mortality rate at 28 days was 12% in the experimental group vs 45% in the control group (p = 0,008)⁴⁶.

An interesting point is that C1INH is the only medication reviewed here acting on blood clotting.

Considering the fact that elevated D-dimers seems to be one of best predictor of bad prognostic, an agent acting on the coagulation pathway could be interesting to investigate further. It seems even more interesting since a study have showed seriously ill patients had a 23% chance of having pulmonary embolisms⁴⁷.

It seems to show a good tolerability. The only side effect we have to be aware of is the risk of thromboembolic events that is reported but seems rare (<1%). Because C1INH is a blood derived product, risks that apply to this kind of product also apply to C1INH.

One potential downside on a population level is the cost of this medication. According to UptoDate, 3000 UI would cost approximately 3300\$. If we take into account that the dose used in Igonin study was 12000 UI, the price could definitely be a limiting factor to the large scale use of C1INH. It could still be used as a 2nd or 3rd line of treatment.

Metformin

Metformin is a well-known and well-studied drug used as first line therapy in type 2 diabetes. It increases insulin sensitivity by “pre-activating” the insulin receptor through its phosphorylation by MAPK. It is also used off-label for PCOS. Its action in PCOS treatment is probably through the upregulation of leptin receptor’s expression, increasing cells’ sensitivity to leptin. It might also explain why metformin is one of the rare treatments for diabetes that causes a small weight loss.

Anti-inflammatory effects of metformin have been known for a long time. It was first thought that they were due to the improvement in blood glucose, but studies have shown since then that this effect was independent of diabetes and blood glucose. Metformin decreases TNF-alpha’s production through the inhibition of macrophage’s scavenger receptors. By inhibiting IL-1beta, it

reduces the release of IL-6 and IL-8 and suppresses the activation of pro-inflammatory phosphokinases (Akt, p38 and Erk)^{48,49}.

A study on mice demonstrated that pulmonary edema, vascular exudate, neutrophils' accumulation in the lungs, TNF-alpha, IL-1b, IL-6, IL-17 were significantly reduced by metformin when sepsis and ARDS were induced by LPS administration. The study also showed that it reduced the mortality rate⁵⁰.

Metformin being already used widely and having a low cost compared to other options, its use should be considered, and studied further.

Conclusion

In this review, we have tried to show that many well-known drugs, even some forgotten ones, might be effective in reducing the risks of developing a severe or critical illness, in preventing its evolution to ARDS and, even, in treating the ARDS, caused by the COVID-19 infection, thus potentially reducing the mortality. We tried to do so by choosing molecules whose actions could be explained biochemically. The molecules needed to be able to either raise ACE2 activity (by upregulating ACE2, activating it or mimicking its action), modulate the leukocytes response (by attenuating neutrophils' action or promoting the T lymphocytes and NK cells responses) or reduce the inflammation (by lowering the pro-inflammatory cytokines and their effects). Most of these molecules had been studied in animal model of ARDS, or other pathologies caused by cytokine storms, or in studies about the SARS-CoV1.

We tried to convince you that the timing of the interventions is probably crucial for the treatment to be effective. Giving vitamin D to a patient with ARDS already in the ICU would probably not

have any effect on the outcome, but giving it to all elderly patients of a nursing home, before anyone get infected, might benefit some by reducing the illness's severity and might prevent some severe cases of evolving up to ARDS. We do not recommend prescribing Metformin and a ACEI to a 25 years old woman with no health issue, but might consider doing so for a 62 years old patient who just retired and have received lab results showing a pre-diabetic state and having a blood pressure that is always at the upper limit of the acceptable range and that told his family doctor he would start going to the gym on his last appointment.

We also tried to warn you not to hope for a miracle drug. A drug blocking every pathway used by the virus to cause inflammation, but, yet, not suppressing our immune system completely, to still be able to eliminate the virus and to defend against opportunistic infections, might not be discovered soon. Has a really effective drug, curing the disease, stopping the symptoms and preventing every complication, against the seasonal flu or the common cold, been discovered yet? On the other hand, using multiple molecules, each blocking a specific pathway or enhancing a part of a well-adapted defense mechanism, might not cure the disease or prevent every death, but might improve the mortality rate and save lives. We think that this objective should be the one to pursue; to find all the tools that could be used by physicians, and some guidelines stating the best way to use them, and then to let them use their clinical judgement to give the best drugs' combination possible for the patient they are treating; just like they already do for many ailments and diseases, from chronic pain to diabetes.

As for the production of a vaccine, many questions still remain. Even when it will be produced, its efficacy in stopping the propagation and preventing the infection or reducing the severity of the illness will still have to be proven. The SARS-CoV2 being a RNA virus, its mutation rate is fast and nothing can assure us that the virus we will have to deal with in 6, 12 or 18 months will still be recognized by the acquired immunity of a vaccinated patient. A different vaccine against the

influenza virus needs to be produced each year; and, some years, we are not that successful in producing a really effective one. Why would the SARS-CoV2 be any different? It has already mutated and the strain actually in Asia is different than the one in Europe which is also different than the dominant one in America. Will a vaccine be able to cover all those strains and the future ones? It will probably depend on the target chosen to produce the vaccine and how well it is preserved even through the virus multiple mutations. The S-spike seems like the best target; its mutation would make the virus much less dangerous and an humoral protection against this specific target would prevent the virus entry into our cells.

Even if we think that these researches need to be continued, we have other objectives in mind to help reducing the burden of the disease quickly. Clinical studies should be started to evaluate the effectiveness of diminazen aceturate and montelukast in reducing COVID19's mortality rate. The studies should be large enough to be able to determine to which patients they benefit the most and what is the optimal timing to administrate them. Giving a good treatment to a patient with high risk of deterioration, but not to low risk ones, at the right time, not when it's already too late, would result in a smaller NNT and a better cost-effectiveness ratio.

We also think that large doses of Vitamin D should be given to nursing home residents, health care providers, first responders and essential service workers. The Afro-American population, or even, all the citizens of a state with darker skin color than that geographic localisation's native population should probably take supplementation, because a darker skin means a better protection against UV radiation but also less production of vitamin D from sunlight. The skin color has adapted for ages to balance the production of vitamin D and the protection of the folic acid from the sun's radiation, and the optimal color differs depending of the geographic location and solar irradiation exposure. With globalization, people are moving to other areas of the world and have really different sunlight exposure compared to the one their ancestries had, causing

imbalances even many generations later and much more frequent and profound vitamin D deficiencies.

In the emergency room and hospital settings, we should test for vitamin D deficiency in every patient who consult for COVID19-related symptoms and replete with a loading dose followed by maintenance doses if in deficiency. Studies measuring the efficacy of these 2 public health policies should be done at the same time. The target blood level should be between 100 nmol/L and 150 nmol/L.

Further research is needed to identify every medication that could be useful and to create decision tools to help health professionals use them optimally. We need to do these research to reduce SARS-CoV 2 mortality and morbidity, but also to be prepared to face the next “new” CoV infection causing a severe disease that will eventually appear, 5, 10 or 15 years from now.

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